

First records of a new Europe's southernmost glacier found in Southern Albania

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Abstract

Several perennial snow and ice bodies have been recently studied and monitored in three mountain massifs across the Balkan Peninsula: Prokletije (Northern Albania), Durmitor (Montenegro) and Pirin (Bulgaria), the two glacierets in the Pirin Mountains until soon considered as southernmost of their kind in Europe. In September 2022 a relatively large snow field (about 1.5 ha) was discovered and described for a first time in the glacial cirque Gryka e Kazanit in the Nëmërçka Mountains of Southern Albania. The snow accumulation lies on 1550–1650 m a.s.l. below a vertical limestone cliff with a height of almost 1000 m. The site was visited again in November 2023, when the snow field diminished its size to less than 1 ha. At the same time, multi-annual firn layers were exposed under the last year snow, with depth at least several metres, and indications were observed of ice, buried in the debris cover below. Newest findings indicate that the studied snow-firn body is a glacieret similar to those found in the Pirin Mountains. On a longer-term, nine perennial snow/firn bodies on the Balkans resemble small glaciers rather than snow and ice patches at least under current climatic conditions. Situated on 40°08' Northern latitude, the newly discovered Nemërçka Glacieret is nominated to be the southernmost glacier in Europe.

Key words: Climate, firn, glacieret, limestone, Nëmërçka Mountains, snow

Academic editor: Alexander Gikov

Received: 05 February 2024

Accepted: 22 April 2024

Published: 23 May 2024

Citation: Gachev E, Meshini E, Matev S, Iliev M, Gachev G, Gacheva M (2024) First records of a new Europe's southernmost glacier found in Southern Albania. *Journal of the Bulgarian Geographical Society* 50: 75–94. <https://doi.org/10.3897/jbgs.e120301>

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1. Introduction

Glaciers are among natural bodies that have been mostly affected by climate change. Mountain glaciers all over the world have undergone a rapid shrinkage in the recent decades, and a mass loss without precedent for the last 150 years (Chapter 9, IPCC 2023). The main reason for the observed drastic changes is the rise of temperatures, which has been progressing with an increased pace for the last 30–40 years.

In Europe, besides the classic valley and cirque mountain glaciers and mountain caps, which still cover considerable areas in the Alps, the Greater Caucasus, the Scandinavian Mountains, Iceland, and still lesser areas in the Pyre-

nees, there are many very small forms of present-day glaciation, which appear in the mentioned high mountain ranges, but are also found more to the south, in the mountains that encompass the northern shores of the Mediterranean Sea (Grunewald and Scheithauer 2010; Hughes 2014).

Although such tiny forms make in fact no valuable contribution to the water resources, in recent years, these very small glaciers have been subject to a greater attention by the researchers, because they react very quickly and promptly to short-term variations of climate, and their observation allows for regional comparisons of the reaction of local climate in response of global changes. Small glaciers have demonstrated remarkable resilience to climate compared to their larger counterparts, due to the very strong effect of the local topography. One interesting question is to what extent such effects can counteract the regional geographical conditions: how unfavourable can the regional climate be to still be able to support the preservation of a glacier, especially in the present conditions of temperature warming?

In Southeastern Europe and the Balkan Peninsula in particular, a number of small firn and ice bodies have been recently recorded to exist and persist in some of the highest mountain massifs (Hughes 2008, 2009; Grunewald and Scheithauer 2010; Djurović 2012; Gachev et al. 2016; Gachev 2017, 2023).

Such tiny bodies of snow, firn and ice lie in fact on the transition between classical mountain valley and cirque glaciers, and seasonal snowpack. Among these, three main categories may be distinguished: (very) small glaciers, ice patches and snow patches.

Small glaciers are tiny bodies with areas below 0.5 km² (50 ha) (Huss and Fischer 2016; Arie et al. 2022), which are predominantly made of firn, and can contain snow from the last years on the top and some glacial ice at the base. Having thickness in order of 10–20 and more metres, these small forms match the two main criteria for a glacier: permanence in time (evidenced also by the presence of glacial ice) and indications of dynamic motion of the firn-ice mass. Mainly on the basis of their morphology, small glaciers are divided into small cirque glaciers and glacierets (microglaciers) (Gachev 2023).

Small cirque glaciers are closer to classical glaciers than glacierets. They have a concave shaped higher section and a convex lower section which resembles glacial tongue. As appearance, glacierets look static, because due to the small volume, the motion in them is very slow. They do not have shaped glacial tongue, their surface is uniform (either concave, straight or convex) and their width is often greater than their length. However, dynamic motion in them is indicated indirectly, by either the presence of glacially abraded rocks or by the downward shift of the inclination of sediment layers in the firn-ice mass from parallel to the slope in the upper part, to reverse in the lower (Gądek and Kotyrba 2003, 2007; Grunewald and Scheithauer 2008, 2010, 2011; Gachev et al. 2016).

Glacial ice patches are bodies of stagnant ice, usually partly covered by rock debris fallen from the surrounding rock walls (Serrano et al. 2011). They evolved from former glaciers, when the snow input is too low to support glacial motion. The firn and ice in such patches can be centuries to millennia old (Sakai et al. 2006; Meulendyk et al. 2012; Ødegård et al. 2017).

A snow patch is any accumulation of snow that lasts longer than the seasonal thaw of the snow cover (Higuchi et al. 1980; Wahren et al. 2001; Fujita et al. 2010; Cogley et al. 2011; Parry and Balmer 2017). Snow patches differ by

their longevity (from lasting few weeks more than the period of seasonal snow cover thaw, to perennial), and topographic setting (slope foot, couloir bottom, etc.), but they have two distinct characteristics: they consist predominantly of snow; and do not simultaneously satisfy the two main conditions for a glacier—permanence in time and presence of dynamic motion (Berrisford 1991; Serrano et al. 2011; Plyusnin et al. 2013; Perşoiu and Onac 2018; Hughes 2018; Gachev 2023). Ice patches and glacierets are by default perennial forms.

A total of ten small glaciers (two small cirque glaciers and eight glacierets) have been known to currently exist in the high mountains of the Balkan Peninsula (Onaca et al. 2022; Gachev 2023). Until the middle of the 2010s, their number was estimated to be sixteen (Gachev et al. 2016), but due to climate change several of them gradually degraded to glacial ice patches. Small glaciers in the mountains of the Balkan Peninsula are considered among the southernmost in Europe, until soon the glacierets Snezhnika and Banski suhodol in Pirin being the only that have been known to currently exist south of the parallel 42°N (Grunewald and Scheithauer 2010; Gachev 2017). In 2022 however, a new snow/firn body, previously unmentioned by science, was discovered, observed, photographed and measured in the Nemërçka Mountains of Southern Albania.

The small glaciers on the Balkans are underrepresented in global glacial inventories. Data about them is neither present in the database of WGMS (World Glacier Monitoring Service), nor in the Randolph Glacier Inventory.

Due to climate change (rising temperatures and increase in the share of rain precipitation), for the last several years all of the observed small glaciers have shown mid- to long-term signs of shrinkage, demonstrated by the decrease of their moving average areas. In many years of the last decade (2017, 2019, 2020, 2022, 2023) many of them resembled stagnant ice patches rather than glaciers (Gachev 2023). On the background of this situation, it was quite surprising to discover another glacieret further south, with considerable size compared to other similar forms throughout the region and in the lowest altitude not only in the Balkan Peninsula, but most probably also in all Central and Southeastern Europe.

The present paper is the first scientific publication to announce this discovery. The aim of the study is to introduce the recently found glacieret to the global scientific community, as well as to analyze the supporting factors for its recent existence and survival. The paper summarizes observations and results from two visits in the central part of Nemërçka Mountains, around the end of glacier mass balance year: in September 2022 and in November 2023, in result of which the presence of a small glacier (glacieret) has been confirmed. An attempt is made to explain the extraordinary location of the newly found glacieret with the unique local topographic and climatic conditions of the area.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. Case study area

Nemërçka Mountain is part of the vast Pindus Range which runs in NNW-SSE direction along the western (Adriatic/Ionian Sea) shores of the Balkan Peninsula. The Pindus mountain system is bordered to the north by the valley of Drin River, and to the south it spreads along continental Greece, Peloponnese Peninsula and continues in the Hellenic Island Arc. The system itself is consti-

tuted of three ranges, relatively parallel to each other: Coastal Range (on the Ionian Islands), middle (Gavrovo-Tripoli) range, and Eastern (Pindus) range (Ivanov 2018). Nemërçka belongs to the central range. To the northwest it has an orographic connection with the Dhëmbel Mountains (2050 m a.s.l.) through the 600 m high Dhëmbel Pass, while to the southeast a system of low ridges and passes represents a link to Timfy Mountains (2487 m).

The Nemërçka Range itself is 22 km long and relatively narrow (8–10 km wide). To the northeast it is bordered by the straight graben valley of Vjosa (Aos) River, which upstream flows through the tectonic depression of Konitsa (Zagori). To the southwest lies a depression corridor belonging to different river catchments, which separates the Trëbëshinj-Dhëmbel-Nëmerçka from the neighbouring parallel Shëndëll-Lunxhëria-Buret Range (Fig. 1). Although small

Figure 1. General view and geographical location of Nemërçka Mountains. **A** Nemërçka Mountain range. A view towards northwest from the town of Konitsa (Greece), November 2023. **B** map of the wider area where Nemërçka Mountains is situated **C** map of Nemërçka Mountains and the adjacent ridges and valleys.

in area, Nemërçka Mountains are the fourth highest in Albania (after Korab, Prokletije and Gramos), with its highest peak Papingo (in Albanian: Maja e Papingut or Maja e Drittes) reaching as high as 2484 m a.s.l.

The geological composition and structure of Nemërçka Mountains was mentioned already in the 1920s by the prominent German geographer Herbert Louis (Louis 1927). The Nemërçka Mountains, together with its neighbours to the northwest, Dhëmbel and Trëbëshinj Mountains, represent an elongated anticline built of cretaceous carbonate sedimentary rocks: limestone, limestone flysch, marls and dolomites (Meco and Aliaj 2000).

The mountains were glaciated during the Pleistocene, as the snow line at that time regionally reached as low as 1800 m a.s.l. (Paul and Schafer-Neth 2003; Hayes et al. 2005). Due to the westerly prevailing winds, accumulation of ice and glacial erosion occurred only on the leeward (NE) slope in the higher southern section of the mountain range (Fig. 2). One huge and very deep glacio-karstic depression, Gryka e Kazanit, was formed to the north-east of the highest peak, and several smaller glacial depressions surround it (most of them to the south from the main cirque). It appears that lithology has played a crucial role in the shaping of glacial relief, as the NE slope is built mainly of finely layered flysch rocks. Due to the folding process which occurred during orogenesis, the rocks were probably heavily cracked in direction along the main ridge, and those cracks served as breaking lines for the glacial erosion on the leeward mountain side. As a result, a highly asymmetric relief was formed, a steep, long but straight and relatively flat slope to the southwest, and a step-

Figure 2. The highest section of Nemërçka Range, rising above Vjosa River valley. A view from south-east.

wise slope to the northeast with a series of 400–800 m high cliffs along its upper section. Short glacial valleys descend on the NE side, some reaching the mountain foot.

2.2. Methods

The site of the larger (southern) snow field in the Gryka e Kazanit cirque of Nemërçka Mountains was visited twice: on September 13, 2022 and on November 9, 2023. A detail look on the snow/firn body was done from all directions. Dimensions (length, width) were measured with a laser range finder (LRF) with 900 m range. The bergshrund and hardly accessible locations were investigated by a drone. Results were visualized and analyzed in GIS, and a geomorphological sketch of the glacieret and the landforms in its vicinity was made as it is common in this type of research (Hughes 2007; Rączkowska 2008; Grunewald and Scheithauer 2008; Djurović 2012). Current glacieret outlines were drawn in GIS on the basis of LRF measurements, on-site ground photographs and airborne images taken by the drone. For estimation of glacieret former extents, available satellite images were georeferenced over the map in ArcGIS to retrieve lengths and widths. Photographs taken on land from similar positions were used to visually compare glacier states for the autumns of 2013, 2022 and 2023.

Projected areas for the various time periods were calculated in ArcGIS, and real areas were retrieved from projected areas assuming the average glacieret surface gradient of 25° (such average gradient was recorded during the multi-annual observations of Snezhnika glacieret in the Pirin Mountains, Gachev (2023)).

For the characteristic of climate, meteorological data from the station Konitsa, situated to the southeast from the study area, on the territory of Greece (in fact, 29 km from the study site, the Gryka e Kazanit Cirque) are used. The station, located at 40°02'N, 20°44'E and at altitude of 466 m a.s.l., has the status of synoptic station, operated by the Hellenic National Meteorological Service (HNMS). Data has been used for average minimum and maximum air temperatures, for mean annual air temperature, for annual and monthly amounts of precipitation. Data are averaged for a 54-year period (1956–2010). No reliable information has been found from meteorological stations on Albanian territory.

3. Results

3.1. Environmental conditions for the formation of the glacieret

The great glacio-karstic depression is named Gryka e Kazanit (the Cauldron Neck). It has length of ca. 2 km, and is up to 2 km wide in its highest section (Fig. 3). Its floor is opened to northeast, rising from 900 m near the narrowed outlet to 1600 m a.s.l. at the top of the screes encompassing the cliff base. Gryka e Kazanit is indeed a prominent landform. Morphologically, it can be determined as a complicated cirque-trough (Barr and Spagnuolo 2015): the overall altitude difference within the cirque floor is quite great, but at the same time floor gradients in some sections in the lower part are in the range 11–14°, which is steady enough for a cirque (Evans and Cox 1974). In the upper end of the elongated depression, three cirque-like armchair incisions can be outlined. They are separated by rocky ribs and are filled with scree material. Downslope,

Figure 3. The central part of Nemërčka Mountains with the Gryka e Kazanit glacio-karstic depression. **A** Gryka e Kazanit with 800–1000 m tall rock cliffs, a photograph from the valley of Vjosa River (the snow field is seen at the foot of the big couloir) **B** general map of the cirque and adjacent area.

Gryka e Kazanit ends with a clearly visible rigel at 950–1000 m a.s.l. It is covered by a 20–30 m high cirque moraine, with some large boulders on top. A creek appears below the moraine and forms a spectacular 20 m high waterfall on the limestone rocky step 200 m further down (the Sopot Waterfall). Below

the rocky escarpment where the waterfall is, a short, but deep glacial trough descends towards the valley of Vjosa River. Valley floor is covered with screens, in which the creek disappears shortly downstream from the waterfall. No obvious moraine accumulations are observed on the way down from Gryka e Kazanit outlet.

In the zone of glacio-karstic depression, the axis of the anticline structure of the mountain is crossed also by transverse dislocations oriented NE-SW. The floor of Gryka e Kazanit is surrounded by the highest rock walls in the mountain. Those on south and west stand almost vertical for heights between 850 and 1000 m. These are probably the tallest rock escarpments on the Balkan Peninsula and among the highest in Europe. The central wall to the southwest of the cirque floor is curved in a concave shape, it is 800–850 m high, built of compact limestone, contrary to the cliffs to the south, carved in the tiny flysch layers. Flysch layers on the strongly shaded rock face to the south of the cirque floor is subject to strong frost weathering, which is evidenced by the abundant amounts of fresh fine debris on the rocks. Rock fragments of pebble to boulder size form series of huge debris fans in a concentric pattern around the cliffs. Pebble fraction strongly predominates, which is typical for periglacial fans in limestone (Gachev 2021).

3.2. Morphology of the glacieret

Two snow bodies were found in the cirque in September 2022. The larger one has a triangle fan shape and is situated on the southwest, at the base of the vertical NE wall of the highest peak, Mt. Papingo, at 40°07'48" N and 20°26'00" E. The snow field lies at the foot of a long and narrow couloir which serves as an avalanche track in winter and spring (and is the main supplier of snow). The altitude of the snow field is between 1550 and 1600 m a.s.l. (Fig. 3). The snow surface is surrounded by a protalus-moraine ridge which rises 5 to 10 m above the edge of the snow field (Fig. 4). On the northern side, the snow body

Figure 4. The lower section of snow field bed with the moraine ridge to the right.

Figure 5. A close view to Nemërčka Glacieret. **A** drone footage, 13 September 2022. The darker snow was probably deposited in the winter of 2020/2021, while the white snow in the uppermost section is considered a remnant of 2021/2022 snow accumulation **B** sketch of Nemërčka Glacieret (size as of September 2022).

contacts with the bedrock. The depression in which it lies is open downwards in the lower (northern) end, parallel to the rock wall. There, a huge debris track is formed. Further down, a stadal moraine ridge is observed at about 1300 m (about 300 m from the current snow front). Abundant bottom moraine deposits (large boulders to blocks) cover the central section of the cirque floor, between the stadal moraine and the cirque outlet. Another snow patch is located at 40°08'07" N and 20°25'28" E at 1750–1800 m in the northwestern part of the cirque, in an almost vertical couloir in the rock wall.

During our first visit, in September 2022, the snow patch on the site had a triangular fan-like shape, with length about 250 m (from south to north) and width 150 m (from west to east). (Fig. 5). The bergshrund on the southern side was able to be entered on foot. There the thickness of the snow above ground was about 8 m. The approximate area, calculated on the basis of the measurements, was about 1.57 ha. The snow, probably deposited in the winter of 2020/2021 and 2021/2022, covered all the surface, so the section of the snow patch was seen only from the south (in the bergshrund), where no traces of old snow, firn, or sediment layers were observed, leading to the conclusion that this thick covering snow mass was deposited in a single season (or two at the most). No traces of glacial striations were discovered on the exposed bedrock along the northern side of the snow body.

During our second visit in November 2023, the snow field reduced its size by more than 50% relative to the last year. Its length was about 180 m, while the width accounted to about 90 m, with an area about 0.73 ha. Due to the serious shrinkage, the structure of the snow and firn body was much more exposed. Clear, thick mass of firn with interposing sub-horizontal layers of sediment was observed at its base, reaching to unknown depth in the ground (Fig. 6A). At the lower (northern) side, the snow/firn body thickness above the debris surface was about 4–5 m. Layers of snow, ice, firn and sediment were clearly distinguished, suggesting a multi-annual accumulation (Fig. 6B).

Figure 6. Natural outcrops of the snow/firn body on the 9th of November 2023. **A** exposure of older firn mass with sediment layers at the base of the snow mass from the latest years **B** an outcrop of the glacieret in the lower part, showing layers of snow, ice and firn. Visible height above ground is about 4–5 m.

On the basis of these new findings, we consider the snow/firn body in the southern part of Gryka e Kazanit Cirque of Nemërçka Mountain as a small glacier (glacieret) rather than a snow patch. The lack of glacial striations on the bedrock can be explained by the mechanical weakness of the strongly defragmented and heavily weathered the flysch rock—weakness is also evidenced by the abundant amount of freshly fallen debris from the rock escarpment. Such rock is quite easily eroded instead of polished, which is witnessed by the large amounts of pebble size scree accumulations.

3.3. Data about inter-annual and multi-annual changes of the glacieret

For the period 2022–2023 there has been data from direct observations of the glacieret, as it was already mentioned. Between September 2022 and November 2023, glacieret's length decreased by 28%, and the width shortened by 40%. The surface was 7 to 8 m lower compared to the last year. The height of the snow/firn surface at the uppermost (southern) end lowered by about 8 m, and the snow on the southern side next to the rock wall was leveled to the ground. Even greater decrease (about 10 m surface lowering) was registered in the section near glacieret front. As mentioned above, the total surface area also shrunk by a little more than a half (Fig. 7).

Such inter-annual changes can be considered normal for a glacieret, as they are quite similar to those observed in other small glaciers on the Balkans (Gachev 2020, 2023). Regarding the glacieret sustainability on a longer-term, it was present on all Google Earth satellite images from Gryka e Kazanit site,

Figure 7. Comparative pictures of Nemërçka Glacieret in the autumns of 2013 (a photograph by Anesti Jance), 2022 and 2023 (photographs by Emil Gachev). **A** a distant view **B** a close view.

at least on those, which are clear enough, for example, from October 2011, August 2012, July 2014 and May 2020. The clearest is the image from 4.10.2011, where the glacieret had visible length (from south to north) of about 150 m and a width of up to 50 m. On the image from August 2012, the surface area of the glacieret is similar to what was seen in September 2022, however the level of the snow surface was little lower. The presence of a large snow field is also evident on a base jump video from October 2021 (with a surface area larger than in 2022), and on a series of photographs from 12th of September 2013, taken from the field by the mountaineer Anesti Jance (Fig. 7, top left). On the latter images the glacieret also appears to be much larger than it was in September 2022 and its size is comparable to that in 2021.

On the basis of the on-site measurements and of the calculations based on the satellite images that have sufficient quality, data about the surface area of the glacieret in various moments around the end of glacier mass balance year were obtained (Table 1).

Table 1. Calculated and measured surface areas of Nemërçka glacieret (Projected area is calculated in GIS. Real area is calculated from projected area, assuming an average gradient of glacieret surface of 25°).

Month and year	Method	Area (projected) [ha]	Area (real) [ha]
October 2011	Calculation based on satellite image	0.40	0.44
August 2012	Calculation based on satellite image	1.29	1.43
September 2013	Calculation based on a ground photograph	2.74	3.04
July 2014	Calculation based on satellite image	2.47	2.74
September 2022	On-site measurement (LRF)	1.41	1.57
November 2023	On-site measurement (LRF)	0.66	0.73

The variations are greater in the lowermost segment of the glacieret (Fig. 8). The rock wall and the high moraine restrict fluctuations on their sides.

3.4. Climate conditions

The climate of the Pindus Range in Southern Albania and Northwestern Greece is generally Mediterranean, with mild and rainy winters, relatively warm and dry summers and, generally, extended periods of sunshine throughout most of the year (Zittis et al. 2022). However, a great variety of climate subtypes (all within in the Mediterranean climate frame) are encountered in the area due to the influence of topography (parallel mountain ranges of moderate to high altitude, separated by intra-montane depressions of various size and orientation). The mountain systems are spread generally transverse to the air coming from the moisture sources of the central Mediterranean Sea.

The current climate of Nemërçka Mountains itself is Mediterranean in mountain modification, with precipitation in the surrounding valleys above 1300 mm/y, and supposedly even higher within the mountain range (no climatic stations are situated in the mountain or the surrounding ranges). During the winter, snowfalls are very heavy with drifts of several meter thickness persisting until

Figure 8. Outlines of Nemërčka glacieret for the periods listed in Table 1.

Table 2. Monthly and annual air temperatures (minimum, maximum and average) and precipitation amounts in Konitsa (Greece) for the period 1956–2010 (Hellenic Meteorology Service).

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	Ann.
Tmin (°C)	-0.8	0.3	2.2	5.4	8.3	12	15.2	16.1	12.7	9.4	5.7	1	7.3
Tmax (°C)	6.6	7.9	11.3	15.8	19.9	24.5	28.6	29.4	23.6	18.5	13.4	8.5	17.3
Tavg (°C)	2.4	4.1	6.6	10.6	14.1	18.2	21.9	21.7	18.3	14	9.3	4.7	12.2
Prec. (mm)	112	92	85	67	82	85	49	38	63	77	133	110	993

summer (Duchoň 2018). In general, Furlan (1977) estimated mean temperatures of -5°C and 15°C during the winter and summer months, respectively, for the highest mountain zone of the Pindus above 2000 m a.s.l.

More particular climatic data can be seen in Table 2. We will pay a greater attention to the values for the cold part of the year, from November to March, as this is the period with potential for snow retention in the mid- and high montane zone.

During this period, average temperatures range between 2 and 9°C, indicating far from favourable conditions for snow accumulation. These temperature values however are registered at a site with an altitude below 500 m a.s.l., while the study area, as it was noted above, has an altitude of 1500–1600 m and above. On such altitudes the average temperatures are usually 6 to 8°C lower, when considering the average vertical lapse rate for the free atmosphere, which is 0.65°C decrease for every 100 m rise of altitude (Panchev 1982). Still much lower should be the average temperatures on the top of the mountain ridge, which in the central section of Nëmërçka range spreads above 2000 m a.s.l.

In Konitsa, the precipitation sum for this period is more than 500 mm, but in the mountains it is considerably higher. Depending on the prevailing atmospheric circulation and the slope position according to the moisture air mass invasions (windward/leeward), precipitation can exceed 1000 mm/y. Such quantities, combined with the temperatures that favour precipitation in a solid form, lead to accumulation of snow cover of considerable thickness and density. Warmer air masses from the Mediterranean easily reach these areas, and in winter, relatively warmer episodes have frequent occurrence. During such intervals, which may last for several days to weeks, the snow cover is packed and increased in density, which is a prerequisite for a prolonged melting in spring-summer. The huge amounts of precipitation during the cold half of the year are mostly caused by the passage of Mediterranean cyclones. Their frontal zones cause intense precipitation, which appear as snow in the high central parts of the prominent ranges. When temperatures are close to zero the snow is wet and dense, and can instantly generate a snow cover with higher density. On the other hand, the almost vertical cliffs in the upper section of the NE slope of Nëmërçka Range (including in the section directly above the glacieret) provide for very intense avalanche activity. The funnel shape of Gryka e Kazanit cirque additionally supports concentration of enormous snow amounts over a relatively small area, which can lead to extreme snow thickness in winter (here we can point out the example of Snezhnika Glacieret in Bulgaria, where the snow piles up to 20 m thickness, Popov (1964)). Nëmërçka Glacieret itself is situated at the base of a slope couloir (gully) that additionally concentrates the avalanche snow. Another factor that additionally enhances snow accumulation in the NE facing cirques of the range, and in particular on the site of the glacieret, are the suggested huge amounts of snow that the prevailing SW winds blow out from the vast gentle SW slope and transfer on the leeward (NE) side of the main ridge. The contribution of this windblown snow is very hard to assess, but there is no doubt that it must be considerable.

The huge amount of accumulated snow is a crucial factor for the all year round glacieret preservation, despite the very low absolute altitude (1550–1650 m a.s.l.). Another important factor is the very steep slopes that rise to the south and west of the glacieret. On one hand they block the direct sunlight, and on the other, provide for a faster radiation cooling in the warm half of the year, during nights with a clear sky. In summer, the steep surrounding cliffs provide for the descent of cold air, which undergoes radiation cooling still along the upper section of the cliff. Such cold air streams hinder the melt of snow and ice still before the fall of darkness.

Glacieret's surroundings indicate that the area permanently covered by snow and ice must have had much larger extent in the past. Having in mind Nëmërç-

ka Glacieret's relatively large size in the autumn of 2023, when all monitored small glaciers and snow patches on the Balkans were in decline, we should definitely consider this form as small glacier, the southernmost in Europe. The other snow patch, which is situated in the northern section of Gryka e Kazanit cirque, is rather a (possibly permanent) snow patch—much smaller in size and most probably stagnant.

4. Discussion

The newly discovered glacieret is among the eleven features of this type, registered in the mountains of the Balkan Peninsula (Fig. 9)—the others being located in the Pirin Mountains of Bulgaria (two small glaciers), in Prokletije Massif in Albania (seven small glaciers) and in Durmitor, Montenegro (one small glacier). All these permanent bodies of snow, form and ice, exist on sites located far below the present-day climatic snow line for the free atmosphere, due to the influence of specific topography. Especially for the Balkan Peninsula, common factors that are considered to support glacier existence and survival are the relict glacial landforms from the Pleistocene (deep shaded cirques) and the car-

Figure 9. Locations of present-day small glaciers, snow and ice patches in the mountains of Southeastern Europe, the southeastern periphery of the Alps and the Apennine Peninsula.

bonate bedrock which exerts a favourable effect on the preservation of perennial snow in three aspects: light colour, which provides for a greater albedo and colder surface conditions compared to other rocks, such as silicate magmatic or metamorphic rocks; water permeability due to karstic corrosion, which is associated with deficit of meltwaters on the bottom of the snow bodies during the melt in spring-summer; and the mechanism of karstic corrosion and its active progression over time, which resulted in creation of deep glacio-karstic depressions (cirques-dolines) with high, almost vertical rock walls. The optimal combination of all these conditions has produced a local drop of the regional climatic snow by 600 to 800 m on several sites in the high mountains on the Balkan Peninsula, and to the formation of glaciers, which, although very small in size when compared to the glaciers in the Alps, match the two most essential criteria for a glacier: persistence in time and signs of dynamic motion. In this regard, the environmental background that has supported the existence of a glacieret in Gryka e Kazanit cirque of Nemërçka Mountains is even more unique and interesting, as in this case the drop of the regional snow line on the particular site is by more than 1200 m.

In its overall appearance and in the structure of its snow-firn mass, the glacieret in the Gryka e Kazanit cirque is quite similar to Snezhnika glacieret under Vihren peak in the Pirin Mountains. Its existence on such an unusual place is favoured by unique combination of topographic and climatic conditions, topography being the most important in this particular case. The presence of a vertical cliff almost 1 km tall is a very rare phenomenon, especially for a mountain about 2.5 km high. The high rock walls and the generally closed configuration of the relict glacio-karstic depression (Gryka e Kazanit) provide conditions for the preservation of all year round snow at extremely low altitude (1550–1600 m), in fact in the zone of deciduous forests—there are beech trees at the same altitude as the glacieret, not far from it. Nemërçka glacieret is located at 40°08' northern latitude, 1°32' more to the south than Snezhnika glacieret, which has been considered currently as the southernmost glacial mass in Europe by the international scientific community (Grunewald and Scheithauer 2008, 2010).

Besides the influence of topography, which plays a major role for the formation of the glacieret, also of a crucial importance is the considerable amount of winter precipitation. In its high zone, the steadier and smoother southwestern slope serves as a vital source area for avalanche and windblown snow, providing very thick accumulations at the NE foot of the rock escarpment. The very strong shading from three sides results in specific microclimatic conditions, which cannot be evaluated adequately by just extrapolating data from nearby climatic stations. Temperature conditions in the vicinity of the glacieret are expected to be far more severe than what is inferred for the free atmosphere. Here we can refer to the studies of Snezhnika glacieret in Pirin (Gachev 2023), where the sums of daily positive temperatures on the surface near the glacieret surrounding moraine, are on average 2 to 2.8 times smaller than what was extrapolated for the same altitude based on remote data and following the standard lapse rate. All these circumstances make estimation of local climatic conditions quite uncertain. To better understand the specific climatic factors, continuous on site measurements are necessary.

Located so low, far below 2000 m a.s.l., Nemërçka glacieret has avalanching as main factor for its formation and survival in the current conditions of climate

warming. It is expected that this small glacier is particularly greatly dependent on precipitation (especially winter precipitation), and this makes predictions of its longer-term dynamics and evolution highly uncertain at this stage.

5. Conclusion

In result of two expeditions, which took place at the end of glacier mass balance year in 2022–2023, it was revealed that two snow-firn bodies exist in the cirque Gryka e Kazanit in the Nemërçka Mountains of Southern Albania. Based on our detail observations, we consider the largest of them, situated in the south-western end of cirque floor, as a current small glacier (glacieret), quite similar to the well-known Sneznika glacieret in the Pirin Mountains of Bulgaria. The newly found glacieret exists under geographical conditions that are in some aspects unique in the Balkan region and in Southeastern Europe as a whole. The presence of an almost vertical limestone rock cliff with relative height of almost 1000 m, along with the considerable amounts of precipitation, enable the persistence of all year round snow and firn at altitudes of 1550–1600 m above sea level, which is additionally favoured by the presence of steady snow accumulation surface to the south-west of the main ridge, as well as by a rock couloir to concentrate avalanche snow.

Despite the relatively low absolute altitude, the all year round preservation of snow and ice on the floor of Gryka e Kazanit cirque has been possible because of the great absolute amount of precipitation during the cold half of the year. The accumulation of an extremely thick cover of dense wet snow with a high water content is favoured by the intense snowfalls and the not so low temperatures, as well as by the frequently occurring warming episodes between snow accumulation events. The role of all these favourable conditions is enhanced by the unique topographic conditions on the site of the glacieret, which support the additional concentration of the snow. Additional role for the snow retention plays the strong shading and the good radiation cooling during clear nights in summer.

The newly discovered glacieret is at the same time the southernmost and the lowermost feature of this kind in the whole Southeastern Europe. Further research is recommended (including geophysical studies and local climatic monitoring) to better evaluate the type of this form and the environmental conditions for its formation and preservation.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

Data curation: EG, SM. Formal analysis: SM. Investigation: GG, EG, EM, MG, MI. Methodology: SM. Resources: EM. Writing - original draft: SM, EG.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.